

Synthesis of Some New 5-Aryl/Aryloxymethyl-2-Chloro-1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and their Oxadiazoloquinazolone Derivatives as Potential Pesticides

H. SINGH*,

Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur-273 001

L. D. S. YADAV

† Tokyo Institute of Technology, Midori-Ku, Yokohama, 227, Japan
and

B. K. BHATTACHARYA

† K. U. L., Laboratorium Voor Organische Scheikunde, Celestijnenlaan 200 F, B-3030, Heverlee, Belgium

Manuscript received 2 December 1980, revised 19 October 1982, accepted 20 May 1983

Several 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-2-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III) have been prepared by treating 2-aryl/aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (IIa) with $\text{POCl}_3/\text{PCl}_5$. The latter were prepared by cyclisation of their corresponding N-aryl/aryloxyacetylureas with NaOBr/NaOH . The 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-2-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III) have been condensed with anthranilic or substituted anthranilic acid to yield 2-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo[2,3-b]quinazol-5-ones (IV). Eleven of these compounds have been screened and compared with 2,4-D and Dithane M-45 for their herbicidal and fungicidal activities, respectively against two weeds *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*, and two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Based on the screening data a possible activity relationship has been given.

THE chlorine substituted heterocycles are associated with antifungal¹, antibacterial² and herbicidal³ properties. Various chlorine substituted heterocycles are known to display useful pesticidal activities¹⁻⁴. The 3-chloro-5-methyl-1,2,4-triazole is effective as post-emergence herbicide for combating dicotyl plants like *Solanum lycopersicum*, *Sinapisurens* and *Apium graveolens*⁵. Furthermore, 4-imino-3-(polymethyleneimino) quinazolin-2-ones have been reported to have herbicidal properties⁶. The quinazolone derivatives have been patented as acaricides with long lasting larvicidal activities⁶.

Considering above facts, it was thought that the introduction of chlorine into biologically versatile 1,3,4-oxadiazole⁷⁻¹⁰ ring might lead to the improvement of the pesticidal activity. Therefore, 2-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III) have been synthesised. Oxadiazoloquinazolone derivatives (IV) have been prepared with a view to combining the pesticidal qualities of both 1,3,4-oxadiazole and quinazolone nuclei.

The 2-chlorooxadiazoles and oxadiazoloquinazolone derivatives were compared with 2,4-D (sodium salt) and Dithane M-45 (Manganous ethylenbisdithiocarbamate with zinc ion) for their herbicidal

and fungicidal activities against two weeds *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*, and two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* as these have hardly been studied. The title compounds have been synthesised according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

*For correspondence.

†Present address

2-Aryl/aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (IIa) were prepared by cyclisation of N-aryl/aryloxyacetylureas (I) with NaOBr/NaOH. The 1,3,4-oxadiazolinones when treated with $\text{POCl}_3/\text{PCl}_5$, afforded 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-2-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III) which when condensed with anthranilic acid or substituted anthranilic acid, furnished the 2-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo [2,3-b]quinazol-5-ones (IV). The structure of the compounds were supported by ir, nmr and elemental analyses.

The ir spectra of IIa exhibited strong C=O bands at $1690\text{-}1710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and medium NH bands at $3440\text{-}3445, 3140\text{-}3160\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Disappearance of these bands in the ir spectra of III is compatible with their assigned structure. The ir spectra of compounds IV showed a sharp C=O band around 1680 cm^{-1} . In addition, all the compounds exhibited bands due to cyclic C=O and aromatic nucleus in the expected regions.

In the nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) of IV, the aromatic protons (7H) appeared as complex multiplets in the region $1.9\text{-}2.6\tau$ (ppm) and $-\text{OCH}_2-$ protons exhibited a singlet at 5.1τ (ppm) confirming the structure of these compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr disc, and nmr on 60 MHz spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. The chemical shifts are reported in τ (ppm).

N-Aryl/aryloxyacetylureas (I): These were prepared by the standard methods^{11,12}.

2-Aryl/aryloxymethyl- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-ones (IIa)¹³: I (0.1M) was added portionwise with stirring to an ice-cold solution of NaOH (2N, 168 ml) and bromine (17.6 g). The mixture was poured into water after 15 min to yield IIa, which were recrystallised from ethanol and recorded in Table 1.

5-Aryl/aryloxymethyl-2-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III)¹⁴: IIa (0.1 M) was refluxed in a mixture of PCl_5 (0.09 M) and POCl_3 (50 ml) for 5 h at 140° on oil bath. The excess of POCl_3 was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with ice-water to furnish the desired product. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from ethanol. Results of III are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 1—2-ARYL/ARYLOXYMETHYL- Δ^2 -1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLIN-5-ONES (IIa)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %, Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1	Phenyl	250	85	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	59.02 (59.26)	3.45 (3.70)	17.81 (17.22)
2	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	86	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	48.23 (48.85)	2.67 (2.54)	14.39 (14.25)
3	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	72	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2^a$	48.85 (48.85)	2.32 (2.54)	14.12 (14.25)
4	Phenoxyethyl	164	85	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^b$	55.89 (56.25)	4.47 (4.16)	14.61 (14.58)
5	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenoxyethyl	165-166	80	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2^c$	47.49 (47.68)	3.40 (3.09)	12.31 (12.36)

Significant IR bands (cm^{-1} , KBr disc)

	C-N	C-O-C	C-O cyclic	N-H	Substituted benzene nucleus
a	1660	1010, 1270	1690	3445, 3160	1465, 835
b	1615	1260, 1040	1717	3440, 3140	1500, 770, 710
c	1615	1020, 1250	1710	3440, 3160	1510, 1470, 730

TABLE 2—5-ARYL/ARYLOXYMETHYL-2-CHLORO-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLES (III)

Sl. N.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %, Found/(Calcd.)	
					N	Cl
1	Phenyl	250	75	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}$	15.46 (15.51)	19.55 (19.67)
2	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	80	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}$	13.00 (13.02)	33.00 (33.02)
3	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	85	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}^a$	13.12 (13.02)	33.25 (33.02)
4	Phenoxyethyl	140	80	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	13.26 (13.30)	16.75 (16.86)
5	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenoxyethyl	125-130	88	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	11.67 (11.43)	30.01 (29.98)

Significant IR bands (cm^{-1} , KBr disc)

	Oxadiazole ring		C-C	Substituted benzene nucleus
	C-N	C-O-C		
a	1665	1270, 1040	750	1585, 1450, 840

2-Aryl[aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo [2,3-b] quina-
zolo-5-ones (IV): An equimolar mixture of 2-chloro-
rooxadiazole and anthranilic acid was refluxed in
glacial acetic acid for 1 h. The resulting mixture
was cooled, poured into water, and the crude pro-
duct thus obtained was filtered washed with water
and recrystallised from ethanol-acetone (60 : 40 v/v).
Results are recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

Herbicial screening : The test weeds were *Arge-
mone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*. The herbici-
dal activity was evaluated by pre-emergence test, at
three concentrations (1000, 100, and 10 ppm) and
the number of replications in each case was three.
Seeds/tubers of test weeds were soaked for 24 h in
the test solutions and then planted. 2,4-D (sodium
salt) was also tested under the similar conditions

TABLE 3—2-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLO[2,3-b]QUINAZOL-5-ONES (IV)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	m.p.	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %, Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
6	H	H	250	65	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	60.28 (60.30)	3.01 (3.01)	14.31 (14.07)
7	H	7-Br	232	72	C ₁₁ H ₈ BrN ₃ O ₃	52.58 (52.63)	2.51 (2.34)	12.74 (12.28)
8	H	7,9-Br ₂	215	74	C ₁₁ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₃	42.39 (42.76)	1.66 (1.66)	10.20 (9.98)
9	<i>o</i> -Chloro	H	235	80	C ₁₁ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₃	60.67 (60.50)	2.52 (2.69)	14.43 (14.12)
10	<i>o</i> -Chloro	7-Br	210	85	C ₁₁ H ₇ BrClN ₃ O ₃	47.80 (47.81)	2.01 (1.86)	11.26 (11.16)
11	<i>o</i> -Chloro	7,9-Br ₂	250*	82	C ₁₁ H ₆ Br ₂ ClN ₃ O ₃ ^a	39.84 (39.52)	1.54 (1.32)	9.33 (9.22)
12	<i>p</i> -Chloro	H	207	75	C ₁₁ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₃ ^b	60.33 (60.50)	2.55 (2.69)	14.22 (14.22)
13	<i>p</i> -Chloro	7-Br	195*	83	C ₁₁ H ₇ BrClN ₃ O ₃ ^c	47.81 (47.81)	1.98 (1.86)	11.35 (11.16)
14	<i>p</i> -Chloro	7,9-Br ₂	204	90	C ₁₁ H ₆ Br ₂ ClN ₃ O ₃	39.65 (39.52)	1.35 (1.32)	9.35 (9.22)

* Decomposed.

Significant IR bands (cm⁻¹, Nujol mull)

	Oxadiazole ring		C=O	Substituted benzene nucleus
	C=N	C-O-C		
a	1610	1235, 1020	1685	1580, 1460, 760
b	1610	1250, 1020	1697	1605, 1440, 860
c	1620	1275, 1020	1685	1602, 1490, 840

NMR spectrum (τ ppm, DMSO-d₆)

	Protons	Chemical shift	Multiplicity
c	Aromatic (7H)	1.9-2.6	Complex multiplet

TABLE 4—2-ARYLOXYMETHYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLO[2,3-b]QUINAZOLO-5-ONES (V)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %, Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
15	H	H	195*	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	65.47 (65.53)	3.65 (3.75)	14.53 (14.33)
16	H	7-Br	218-221*	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₃	51.89 (51.61)	2.58 (2.69)	11.30 (11.29)
17	H	7,9-Br ₂	212-215*	55	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₃ ^a	42.71 (42.57)	2.21 (2.00)	9.45 (9.31)
18	<i>o</i> -Chloro	H	210	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₃	58.79 (58.63)	3.00 (3.05)	13.00 (12.82)
19	<i>o</i> -Chloro	7-Br	224-225	60	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrClN ₃ O ₃ ^b	47.65 (47.23)	2.34 (2.21)	10.41 (10.33)
20	<i>o</i> -Chloro	7,9-Br ₂	223*	63	C ₁₁ H ₈ ClBr ₂ N ₃ O ₃ ^c	39.33 (39.55)	1.60 (1.65)	8.55 (8.65)

* Decomposed.

Significant IR bands (cm⁻¹, Nujol mull)

	Oxadiazole ring		C=O	Substituted benzene nucleus
	C=N	C-O-C		
a	1620	1232, 1070	1680	1580, 1460, 760, 708
c	1620	1235, 1020	1685	1585, 1465, 740

NMR spectrum (τ ppm, DMSO-d₆)

	Protons	Chemical shifts	Multiplicity
b	Aromatic (7H) -OCH ₂ - (2H)	1.9-2.6 5.1	Complex multiplet Singlet

with a view to compare the results. The percentage inhibition by various newly synthesised compounds are recorded in Table 5.

TABLE 5—HERBICIDAL SCREENING

Compound serial as in Tables 2, 3 and 4	Average inhibition, %					
	<i>A. mexicana</i> Conc., ppm			<i>C. rotundus</i> Conc., ppm		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
3	48.5	30.6	10.3	49.5	32.1	11.5
4	61.7	32.9	15.5	60.0	33.8	13.6
5	65.4	34.7	17.1	62.6	34.0	14.2
7	68.9	40.2	19.6	70.2	42.5	22.4
8	72.8	41.5	20.7	73.9	44.6	25.2
13	72.2	42.3	21.8	71.8	43.7	24.0
14	83.3	52.7	30.4	80.2	45.8	27.3
16	98.7	64.5	40.2	95.0	48.2	32.1
17	100	70.2	44.5	96.1	51.1	33.9
19	100	72.5	45.2	96.6	53.5	33.4
20	100	78.4	47.1	97.1	56.6	38.2
2,4-D	100	88.0	68.2	97.2	79.0	57.2

Fungicidal screening: The antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique¹⁵ against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at three concentrations (1000, 100, and 10 ppm). The number of replications in each case was three. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was also tested under similar conditions for comparison. The percentage inhibition by various compounds are recorded in Table 6.

TABLE 6—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound Serial as in Tables 2, 3 and 4	Average inhibition after 96 h, %					
	<i>A. niger</i> Conc., ppm			<i>H. oryzae</i> Conc., ppm		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
3	80.4	65.6	42.2	80.9	61.3	40.8
4	85.6	68.1	45.7	90.4	64.5	43.3
5	100	76.9	55.6	100	70.4	53.2
7	60.2	33.4	19.1	58.1	30.5	16.7
8	62.1	34.5	21.5	60.1	32.0	18.9
13	70.0	55.4	31.9	68.4	41.5	28.3
14	71.8	57.3	33.0	69.0	43.3	31.1
16	65.5	35.7	22.8	60.9	33.4	20.8
17	70.2	98.3	36.4	74.1	40.5	35.4
19	73.7	61.5	40.1	76.9	63.4	43.5
20	78.6	65.7	42.6	82.4	65.5	46.0
Dithane M-45	100	86.0	72.4	96.7	83.1	68.1

Results and Discussion

Out of eleven tested compounds (Tables 5 and 6), it is apparent that the oxadiazoloquinazolones (serial No. 17-20) were more toxic to both the weeds, *A. mexicana* and *C. rotundus*, and less toxic to both the fungi, *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* in comparison to their parent 2-chlorooxadiazoles (No. 3-5), and that the compounds (No. 5 and 16-20) with aryloxymethyl moiety were invariably more fungitoxic than their aryl analogues (No. 3-4) and (No. 7-14). The high fungitoxicity of the 2-chlorooxadiazoles (No. 3-5) might be understandable in light of the fact that in these compounds the chlorine atom directly attached to the oxadiazole ring is reactive, and thus, is capable of reacting with $-NH_2$ and $-SH$ groups of the cellular constituent

similar to that of various fungicides having reactive chlorine atom¹⁶⁻¹⁷.

The compounds (No. 16-20) displayed (Table 5) the herbicidal activity in the range of 2,4-D (sodium salt) against both the weeds at 1000 ppm but their activity decreased abruptly at lower concentrations (100 and 10 ppm). The compounds with *p*-chlorophenyl or *p*-chlorophenoxy moiety (No. 3, 5, 13, 14, 19 and 20) were more potent than the corresponding compounds (No. 4, 7, 8, 16 and 17) with phenoxy or phenyl substituents, and that the 7,9-dibromo-substituted compounds (No. 8, 14, 17 and 20) were active than the corresponding 7-bromosubstituted compounds (No. 7, 13, 16, 19).

The compound (No. 5) seems to be a promising fungicide, as it displayed fungitoxicity of the order of Dithane M-45 against both the fungal species at 1000 ppm, and inhibited their growth >50% at 10 ppm.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head of Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur for providing departmental facilities and Dr. S. P. Mishra, B.H.U., Varanasi for recording ir and elemental analysis, Prof. Dr. G. Hoornaert, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium for help in recording nmr spectra. Thanks are also due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

References

1. Y. HASEGAWA, M. DOYA, H. ITO and T. DOKI, *Jap. Pat.*, 74, 10739, 1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 164737).
2. E. ENDERS, I. HAMMANN, W. BRANDES, P. KRAUS and W. STENDEL, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 637, 692, 1978 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 190800).
3. W. KOCHMANN, C. F. KROEGER, R. MEITHEIN, G. ERFURT, M. PALLAS and H. KRUEGER, *Ger. (East)*, 73, 678, 1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, 75, 19101).
4. S. KAWADW, K. NISHIO and K. TAKITA, *Jap. Kokai*, 74, 04241, 1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 83, 2276).
5. D. L. HUNTER, *U. S. Pat.*, 3, 464, 989, 1969 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 72, 3496).
6. H. KOHL, N. J. DESOUJA, J. PATEL and D. P. DESAI, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 232, 532 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 80, 121007).
7. S. GIRI, H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, 40, 17.
8. Y. OKADA, *Jap. Pat.*, 70, 24, 982, 1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 73, 98953).
9. J. C. DEBOURGE, D. PILLON and S. TERINH, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 361, 613, 1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 91523).
10. H. HAGIMOTO, H. YOSHIKAWA and Y. OKADA, *Jap. Pat.*, 74, 08258, 1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 164760).
11. I. A. PEARL and W. H. DEHN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1377.
12. A. OSTROGOVICH, *Bull. Soc. Stinte Cluji*, 1929, 4, 538 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1930, 24, 2119).
13. RHONE-POULENC S. A., *Neth. Appl.*, 6, 500, 374, 1965 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 64, 3560).
14. H. NAKANO, A. SUGIHARA, M. ITO and S. TSUBOUCHI, *Jap. Pat.*, 8029, 1967 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, 67, 3560).
15. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.
16. H. P. BURCHFIELD and E. STORES, *Contribs. Boyce Thomson Inst.*, 1956 81, 395.
17. R. G. OWENS and B. BLAAK, *Contribs. Boyce Thomson Inst.*, 1960, 20, 475.